

HIGH DEFORMATION CONSOLIDATION PM PROCESSES
FOR A 8090 Al-Li ALLOY COMPOSITE

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High Deformation consolidation PM processes for Al-Li alloy composites use a high degree of deformation and relatively high strain rate for consolidation, eliminating the problem of Li-depletion. Hot extrusion, hot pressing and dynamic explosive consolidation methods were used to produce a 8090 Al-Li composite reinforced by SiCp and short Ni fibres. For the former two processes, a cold isostatic compaction step was used to achieve a pre-consolidation porosity of less than 10%. The results indicate that higher strengths were achieved by further heat treatment, which probably increased the matrix bulk as well as the interfacial bonding strength. The strengthening mechanisms of the particulate reinforcement system was discussed using various models.

INTRODUCTION

HIGH DEFORMATION CONSOLIDATION

Aluminium alloy based composites have found increasing applications as structural materials, with advantages in high specific modulus and better damping properties. Methods to produce these composites include casting and the use of powder metallurgy techniques [1-3]. PM methods has the advantage of consistent mixing, and the possible use of Rapidly Solidified powders. Presently simple sintering, which is energy and time consuming, has been replaced by high strain rate processes such as rolling[3], forging[4], extrusion[5-7] or even dynamic compaction [8]. The main advantages in these processes is the short consolidation time, reducing oxidation to where inert gases is not needed. However, these processes require an initially low compact porosity, which was achieved using a high pressure isostatic press, commonly known as the Cold Isostatic Press (CIP) [7].

The main problem with Al-Li alloy has is its high affinity to form oxides [9-19], even in inert atmospheres [11]. Obviously, there is no process which can avoid oxidation of aluminium surfaces. The presence of Li as an alloying element has also been found to seriously accelerate oxidation [12]. Oxidation is not only hastened by the presence of Li, the oxidation process itself also depletes the Li by diffusing it out of solid solution to form an inter-metallic Li-Al oxide and carbonate [13], both of which due to their incompatible density with Aluminium, forms a porous, unstable and therefore non-protective oxide layer, which tends to enhance further oxidation.

The oxide layer explains the low ductility and fracture toughness often obtained for Al-Li alloys. These brittle oxides along grain boundaries promote early crack nucleation and subsequent crack void coalescence. They inevitably end up either as stringers or continuous thin layers along the grain boundary after consolidation. As a result, early inter granular fracture occurs to reduce the tensile ductility of the matrix [14,15]. Consolidation methods used has therefore to minimize oxidation and be able to break the oxide layer adequately for proper fusion of all the Al-Li particles, and is achieved using high deformation methods. The short heating period minimizes Li depletion and reduces Li based precipitates, maximizing the % Li in solid solution.

REINFORCEMENT SYSTEMS

In terms of processing practicality, particulates offer the most simple reinforcement system. Whilst the increase in hardness may be maximized by its geometry, the increase in strength is probably the least efficient when compared to whiskers, fibers or platelets. For fibers, strength increases are obtained by transfer of load from the matrix to the reinforcement, thus lowering the effective matrix stress [16,17]. For particulates, however, because the very low effective aspect ratio, only a small fraction of the theoretical reinforcement stress can be achieved. The increase in mechanical properties comes instead from their indirect effect in impeding dislocation movements within the metal matrix [18]. The main effects come from

- i. dislocations generated due to thermal expansion incompatibility.
- ii. grain recrystallization followed by restriction of grain growth by impeding of the grain boundaries.
- iii. Crack initiation points.

The role of the matrix-reinforcement interface has been known to influence the mechanical properties of metal matrix composite considerably [29]. Whilst in the case of fiber reinforcement the effect of the interface bonding concerns the ability to effectively transfer load, in the case of particulates, its role is also important. Fibre reinforces a composite by being able to bear much higher loads than the material it replaces. Particulates cannot bear similar high stresses for the same volume of matrix they replace. If the interface bonding is too small, they might in fact act simply as voids, reducing the composite strength in proportion to the fraction of section area they occupy and, for the case of more angular particles, according to the degree of stress concentration points they induce. Given the first two points above, a poor interfacial bonding would also reduce its effect on grain nucleation and growth inhibition, and thermal incompatibility induced dislocation.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The matrix material was gas atomized RS Al-Li 8090 powder from Sumitomo Light Metals (Japan), with the chemical composition indicated in table 1. Three reinforcement systems were compared: SiC_p, SiC_w and Ni short fibers. Mechanical mixing was used to disperse the reinforcements into the matrix powders. A cold isostatic press was used for compaction to 400 MPa for the extruded specimens. The extrusion work was performed using a 32 mm pre-extruded green compact and a 10 mm diameter extrusion die, thus giving an extrusion ratio of 10. The compacted billets were first preheated in a furnace to 500 °C, and transferred to the extrusion press preheated to the same temperature. Dynamic compaction was performed using an explosive forming method. The hot pressing work was done using 50 kN hot press, with precision controlled strain rate, and an attached force transducer. The tool and work pieces were heated simultaneously heated in an enclosed chamber to ensure accurate temperature control. Full densification was achieved using a strain rate of about 3-15 x 10⁻³ s⁻¹ at 500 °C.

Porosity measurements were done using a Leica Quantimet 520 image analyser. A three point bending Dynamic Mechanical Analysis technique was used to measure the bending modulus of the specimens. This was done in a Perkins Elmer DMA-7 analyser, with a low bending load to minimise the effect of non-linearity in bending [25], indicated in figure 2. The extruded rod was wire cut and surface polished to samples measuring 22.0 x 5.0 x 0.5 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the basic difference in the 3 consolidation methods in terms of their strain rate. It is commonly known that Al alloys experiences significant strain hardening effect which typically increases the yield stress and narrows the difference between the yield and ultimate tensile stress. The result of a high strain rate deformation process would therefore be to increase the yield strength of the matrix material. The presence of particulate or whiskers reinforcement would increase this effect, since their presence would increase the stress intensity at least in matrix materials around them.

TABLE 1: STRAIN RATES OF DENSIFICATION PROCESSES

PROCESS	STRAIN RATE (mm/mm s ⁻¹)
Hot Pressing	3-15 x 10 ⁻³
Hot Extrusion	3-5 x 10 ⁻¹
Dynamic Compaction	500-700 s ⁻¹

TABLE 2: COMPARISON OF DENSIFICATION

PROCESS	% DENSIFICATION	POROSITY %
Hot pressing	> 99	< 1
Extrusion SiC _c	> 99	< 1
Extrusion Ni _f	> 99	< 1
Dynamic Compaction	95-97	6-3

Table 2 shows the % densification measurements for the three processes. This is obtained by calculating the theoretical density based on the ratio of matrix/reinforcement used, and comparing the measured density to this value. Table 2 also indicate the measured porosity values, which is given only as accurate as (± 0.5)%, due to the practical limitation in measurement techniques of porosity. The dynamic compaction actually show a significantly higher porosity, resulting in a lower densification. It is probable that the cause of the low values for the dynamically compacted pieces is due to intergranular defects, rather than poor intragranular strength. A high strain rate can significantly increase the intragranular yield strength, but this also means that intergranular plastic deformation necessary for full densification to occur would be harder to achieve. This is ascertained by the relatively low densification obtained in the dynamically compacted piece. Rather than fusing together, the grains are merely mechanically locked in. Both the extrusion and hot pressing processes gave satisfactory porosity and densification results.

Figures 1-3 indicate the respective microstructures of all three processes. The hot pressured process yielded equiaxed grains (figure 1), and even distribution of particles. The extrusion produced elongated structures along the direction of extrusion (figure 2). The dynamically compacted piece actually revealed massively deformed grains (figure 3).

Table 3 indicate the mechanical properties obtained for all three processes, along with the additional Ni short fibres reinforced system. It is apparent that the Ni short fibre system yielded the most increase in all the mechanical strengths, but most of all in the ultimate stress. The reason is likely because of the efficient strengthening mechanism found in the short fiber system, the good adhesion of the interface, and the absence of significant porositie

CONCLUSION

Whilst a higher strain rate process increased the composite mechanical properties, this is dependent on the ability of the matrix powders to sufficient deform and fuse together. This requirement was obtained for both the forging and extrusion process, but lacking in the dynamic compaction technique.

TABLE 3: MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPOSITES

COMPOSITE	Hardness (RHB)	Modulus (GPa)	0.2 % Yield Stress (MPa)	Ultimate Stress (MPa)	Elong- ation(%)
Pressed SiC _p	44	75	380	410	1-2.5
Extruded SiC _p	56	80	320	360	1-2
Extruded Ni _f	42	98	520	680	7-8
Dynamic Compaction	52	0.45	N/M	N/M	N/M

* N/M : Not meaningful

REFERENCES

1. Erich D L, Metal Matrix Composites: Problems, Applications, and Potential in the P/M Industry, Int. J. Powder Metall., Vol 23 (1), 45-54.
2. Saigal A and Leisk G, Mechanical Properties of Alumina reinforced aluminium metal matrix composites, in Microstructural Development and Control in Material Processing, ed. Durham D R and Saigal A, ASME publ. MD-Vol 14, 1990, 115-9.
3. Liu Y L, Hansen N and Jensen D J, Recrystallization Microstructure in Cold Rolled Al Composites Reinforced by SiC Whiskers, Metall. Trans. A, Vol 20A, Sept 1989, 1743-52.
4. Suzuki K, Matsuoka Y and Fujita Y, Workability of SiCw Reinforced Al Alloy and its Applicability to Die Forging, Advanced Technol. of Plasticity, Vol 1, 1990, 229-34.
5. Mukhopadhyay A K, Flower H M and Sheppard T, Development of Microstructure in AA8090 Alloy Produced by Extrusion Processing, Mater. Sci. and Technol., Vol 6, 1990, 461-68.
6. Asanuma H, Hirohashi M and Hayama O, Fabrication of Complicated Shape Metal Matrix composites by Combined Extrusion, Advanced Technol. of Plasticity, Vol 2, 1990, 945-950.
7. Lee H F, Boey F, Khor K A, Tan M J, Gan J, and Loh N L, AL Alloy Composite Using a CIP and Extrusion Approach, J Mater Processing Technol, 29, 1992, 245-253.
8. Kim N J, Raybould D, Bye R L and Das S K, Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of RS Al-Li Alloy Die Forging, Al-Li Alloy V, Proc Fifth Int Conf on Al-Li, Vol 1, ed Starke E A Jr, Sanders T H Jr, Mater and Comp Eng Publ, 1989, 123.
12. Srivatsan T S, Lavernia E J, Mohamed F A, Influence of Oxides on the Properties of PM Al-Li-Cu Alloys, Int J Powder Metall, 26 (4), 1990, 321-334.

Figure 1: Microstructure of hot pressed Al-Li/SiC_p

Figure 2: Microstructure of hot extruded Al-Li/SiC_p

Figure 3: Microstructure of hot extruded Al-Li/Ni_f.

Figure 4: Microstructure of dynamically compacted Al-Li/SiC_w